

Antimicrobial Resistance Pattern of Commonly Isolated Bacterial Pathogens in Intensive Care Unit of a Teaching HospitalAyshi Banerjee¹, Mousumi Kilikdar*², Biswaroop Chatterjee³¹Junior Resident, Department of Microbiology, IQ City Medical College and Hospital Durgapur, West Bengal²Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, IQ City Medical College and Hospital, Durgapur, West Bengal³Professor and Head, Department of Microbiology, IQ City Medical College and Hospital, Durgapur, West Bengal

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Antibiotics are double-edged swords. They save countless lives when used for the right indications; however they also promote the spread of drug resistant strains by exerting selection pressure on microbial populations. The study was done in critical care areas where antibiotics are maximally used and resistance rates are the highest.**Aim:** This study was conducted to evaluate the frequency of antimicrobial resistance of commonly isolated bacterial pathogens in intensive care units (ICUs) of our tertiary-care hospital.**Materials and Methods:** Our retrospective study covers a one-year period from February 2023 to January 2024, and examines records of 750 critically ill adult patients. The species distribution and resistance pattern of clinical isolates from urine, blood, pus, endotracheal tube (ET) aspirate, and broncho-alveolar lavage (BAL) fluid were analysed. Relevant patient particulars were collected from our hospital information system (HIS).**Results:** Out of 750 specimens, 324 (43.2%) were positive for bacterial pathogens. Urine (47.5%) was the commonest specimen followed by blood (29.0%), ET (15.4%), pus (7.4%), and BAL (0.6%). Most of the isolates were Gram-negative bacilli (GNB) including *Escherichia coli* (28.7%), *Klebsiella spp.* (19.1%), *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus baumannii complex* (ACBC) (14.8%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (8.6%). Most Gram-positive isolates were *Enterococcus spp.* (12.03%) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (10.8%). Among Gram-negative bacilli, resistance was most common to third generation cephalosporin (82.6%) and least common to carbapenems (21.6%) and polymyxins (0%). Gram-positive bacteria were most often resistant to fluoroquinolones (74.8%) whereas only 9.5% were resistant to teicoplanin.**Conclusion:** This study showed high levels of antimicrobial resistance in our ICUs. Therefore, vigilant infection control practices and a robust antimicrobial stewardship programme are needed for favourable clinical outcomes.**Keywords:** Intensive Care Unit, Antimicrobial Resistance, Bacterial Pathogens.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The emergence of AMR is of global public health concern. The epicenter of AMR is ICUs [1] where antimicrobials are widely used because the patients there are highly susceptible to various infections due to immunodeficiency, invasive devices and procedures etc. Unfortunately, such extensive use of antibiotics is promoting the emergence and spread of AMR worldwide. However, patterns of resistance do differ from hospital to hospital, and also within different wards and ICUs in the same hospital [2].

In recent times, infections caused by GNB of the ESKAPE group have increased [3], while

Staphylococcus aureus and *Enterococcus* remain the leading Gram-positive pathogens in the ICU, leaving few treatment options for critically ill patients [4],[5].

Hence the present study was conducted to document the antimicrobial resistance pattern of commonly isolated bacterial pathogens in critical care units of our teaching hospital.

Materials and Methods

Place of the study: Department of Microbiology, IQ City Medical College and Hospital, Durgapur, West Bengal

Study design: Cross-sectional, retrospective study.

Study period: 12 months from February 2023 to January 2024

Inclusion Criteria: Adults admitted in ICU

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Age \leq 18 years
2. Pregnancy

Isolation and identification of the clinical isolates: The study examined records of 750 critically ill adult patients admitted in ICU after obtaining institutional ethics committee permission. Depending upon the clinical symptoms, specimens like urine, blood, endotracheal tube (ET) aspirate, pus and broncho-alveolar lavage fluid were collected aseptically and subjected to microscopy and culture. Urine specimens were inoculated on Cysteine Lactose Electrolyte-Deficient (CLED) agar using a calibrated wire loop (0.01mL) and incubated aerobically at 37°C overnight.

Blood samples were inoculated in BD BACTEC bottles for aerobic culture. Positive blood culture bottles and all other non-urine specimens were inoculated on MacConkey agar and 5% sheep blood agar and incubated aerobically at 37°C overnight. Culture plates that exhibited no bacterial growth were further incubated up to 48 hours, except for urine.

Bacterial species were identified by colony characteristics, Gram staining, motility, and appropriate biochemical tests by manual methods and with the help of the MicroScan WalkAway40 Plus (Beckman Coulter, California, USA) if necessary.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing:

Antimicrobial susceptibility was tested by both conventional disc diffusion method and automated system MicroScan WalkAway40 Plus (Beckman Coulter, California, USA). Results were analysed according to CLSI M100, 33rd Edition, 2023. For vancomycin and colistin only MIC values were determined with the automated system.

Data analysis: Demographic data, plus microbial species and antimicrobial resistance data were collected from our hospital information system and exported into a spreadsheet for further analysis. The prevalence of antibiotic resistance was estimated as the proportion of positive results over the entire study sample.

Results

During the period of study, a total of 750 adults were admitted in ICUs, out of whom 324 (43.2%) patients were culture positive and 426 (56.8%) were culture negative. There were 179 male patients and 145 female patients with a median age of 60 years (Table 1). The most common type of sample was urine followed by blood, ET aspirate, pus, and BAL fluid (Table 2). Gram-negative bacilli comprised the majority of isolates and included among others, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, in decreasing order of frequency (Figure 1). Gram-positive bacterial isolates included *Enterococcus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, among others. Figure 2 shows the species distribution in different clinical specimen. Resistance pattern of different organisms is depicted in Figure 3(a) to 3(f).

Table1: Demographic details of culture positive patients

Parameters	Total n=324	ICU n=138	NICU n=56	SICU n=58	CCU n=24	RICU n=48
Gender, n%						
Male	179(55.2%)	94(68.1%)	41(73.2%)	33(56.8%)	17(70.8%)	26(54.1%)
Female	145(44.7%)	44(31.8%)	15(26.7%)	25(43.1%)	7(29.1%)	22(45.8%)
Age						
18-39	48	15	27	3	1	2
40-60	90	33	16	17	14	10
>60	186	82	17	13	43	31
Median	66	68	24	14	38	26

Abbreviations: ICU- Intensive care unit, NICU- Neuro intensive care unit, SICU- Surgical intensive care unit, CCU- Cardiac care unit, RICU- Respiratory intensive care unit.

Table 2: Number of samples obtained along with their percentage

Sample	n=324	Percentage (%)
Urine	154	47.5
Blood	94	29
ET aspirate	50	15.4
Pus	24	7.4
BAL fluid	2	0.6

Figure 1: Percentage of different organisms isolated

Figure 2: Species distribution in different clinical specimen

Figure 3(a): Resistance pattern of *E. coli*

Figure 3(b): Resistance pattern of *Klebsiella pneumonia*

Figure 3(c): Resistance pattern of *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus baumannii* complex

Figure 3(d): Resistance pattern of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Figure 3(e): Resistance pattern of *Enterococcus spp*

Figure 3(f): Resistance pattern of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Discussion

In this study, we evaluated the antibiotic resistance profiles of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens isolated from different clinical

specimens of ICU patients. Our study showed that the commonest Gram-negative organisms were *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus baumannii complex* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Among Gram-positive

bacteria *Enterococcus spp* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were the commonest. Drug resistance was rampant among all these organisms and these results correlate with findings from other studies across the world [6-10].

According to the United States National Nosocomial Infection Surveillance System, different studies from different hospital can show different frequency of infections [11]. Multi drug resistant (MDR) pathogens in ICU are an emerging problem which is associated with increased mortality, morbidity and health care cost. Preventing antimicrobial resistance is the need of the hour which can be accomplished by strict antimicrobial stewardship.

Conclusion

Our study showed emergence of MDR microorganisms among ICU patients. Antimicrobial resistance is a major hindrance in today's treatment option leading to increased morbidity and mortality. Hospital infection control committee (HICC) should put special emphasis on preventing infections in these high-risk areas. De-escalating antibiotics whenever possible is a good strategy to control antimicrobial resistance. Vigilant antibiotic stewardship programme is an urgent necessity, as lesser use of antibiotics today will save more lives in the future.

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